

Volume 6, Issue 7(1), July 2017
International Journal of Multidisciplinary
Educational Research

Published by

Sucharitha Publications

8-43-7/1, Chinna Waltair

Visakhapatnam – 530 017

Andhra Pradesh – India

Email: victorphilosophy@gmail.com

Website: www.ijmer.in

C O N T E N T S

Volume 6

Issue 7(1)

July 2017

S. No		Pg. No
1.	Factors Affecting Internal Efficiency of Secondary Schools of Illu Aba Bor Zone Wubayew Dagne Ayanew, Andualem Mola Maru and Kitessa Chemedo Edossa	1
2.	Status of Doctoral Researches in The Faculty of Education of Banaras Hindu University: A Trend Analysis Shailendra Kumar	23
3.	Environmental Awareness for a Wisdom Society Nilakshi Senapati and Neeta Kalita Barua	34
4.	Education and Socio-Economic Development K.Lokeswararao	43
5.	Tribal Enhancement in India: Role of Government After Independence Peteti Premanandam and Tadde Naga Raju	57
6.	Qualitative Analysis in Research: A Model for Philosophy of Education Alka Macwan	69
7.	Soil Analysis of <i>Moringa Oleifera</i> in Urban and Coastal Area Nimmi Babychan, Reshma J K, Sophia Mole L and Sakhi Prabhachandh	78
8.	Sankranti Panduga Vishistatha G. Venkata Lal	86
9.	Income, Consumption and Saving Pattern of Kadmat Island, Lakshadweep Pazhanisamy.R	91
10.	Hyderabad Natarangam P.Madhu	118
11.	Self Efficacy and Occupational Stress of Special School Teachers Poonam and Shashi Malik	128

SELF EFFICACY AND OCCUPATIONAL STRESS OF SPECIAL SCHOOL TEACHERS

MS. Poonam

Research Scholar
Department of Education
VMLG College, Ghaziabad

Dr. Shashi Malik

Assistant Professor
Department of Education
VMLG College, Ghaziabad

Abstract

The present study was carried out with the main aim of measuring the Self Efficacy and Occupational Stress of teachers working in special schools. The data to assess Self Efficacy was collected by **General Self Efficacy Scale (GSES)**, which was developed by **Jerusalem, and Schwarzer**. An adaptation for Indian conditions was done by **Sud (2002)**. For measuring occupational stress, data was collected by using **Teachers' Job Stressor Scale (TJSS)**, constructed and standardized by **Rathod and Verma (2005)** with the help of purposive random cluster sampling. The findings of the research revealed that high self efficacy was found in special school teachers. Overall mild occupational Stress was also found in special school teachers. Mild over loadedness, role conflict, powerlessness, role ambiguity, motivelessness and frail interpersonal relationship were also found among this group of teachers. No correlation was identified between Occupational Stress and Self Efficacy of Special school teachers.

Key Words: Self Efficacy, Occupational Stress, and Special School Teachers

INTRODUCTION

Education is the only tool to reach the heights of success as well as for the development of a nation. In the present era education doesn't mean only getting the bookish and theoretical knowledge, while bringing

dynamic changes in thought process of an individual. Such Education cannot be realized without competent, dedicated and self confident teachers. To meet such conditions teachers must be mentally healthy and should be free from any kind of stress so that a healthy impact can be placed on students. Occupational stress in teaching is that which a teacher experiences while working. These stresses in turn affect teachers' health physically and mentally. **Pepe, and Addimando (2014)** identified that Special School Teachers (SETs) and General School Teachers (GET) experience different degrees of occupational stress as a result of experiencing different challenging students' behaviours. Self-efficacy is a person's judgment about being able to perform a particular activity. It is a student's "I can" or "I cannot" belief. Self-efficacy reflects how confident students are about performing specific tasks. Self-efficacy is specific to the task being attempted. The concept of self-efficacy was originally coined by **Albert Bandura**. He constituted it as a part of his social-cognitive theory. Teacher efficacy is a teacher's belief in his /her capability to organize and execute courses of action to successfully accomplish specific instructional task, or more simply, his or her capacity to effect student's performances. (**Bandura, 1977, 1995**). **Sharma, Shaukat and Furlonger (2015)** found that teachers with low self-efficacy face more problems with the implementation of inclusive education.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the Self Efficacy of special school teachers.
2. To study the Occupational Stress of special school teachers.
3. To study the impact of Self Efficacy on Occupational Stress of special school teachers.

HYPOTHESIS

H₁: There exists no significant correlation between Occupational stress and self efficacy of Special School Teachers.

SAMPLE SELECTION

The sample consisted of 200 special school teachers selected from 15 schools of Delhi City. Purposive random cluster sampling technique was used. Quantitative approach was taken up for this study. For developing the research work, Descriptive Survey Methodology was adopted.

TOOLS

1. TEACHER'S JOB STRESSORS SCALE (TJSS): This tool was used in the present study to measure the Occupational Stress of Special School Teachers. This tool is developed by **Rathod and Verma in 2005**. It includes six dimensions of stress faced by the school teachers as Overloadedness, Role conflict, Powerlessness, Role ambiguity, Motivelessness and Frail interpersonal relationship. Total 49 items are included under six dimensions.

2. GENERAL SELF EFFICACY SCALE-HINDI (GSES): This scale is a self-reporting ten item scale. The German scale was developed by **Jerusalem, M. and Schwarzer,R.** in 2002. An adaptation for Indian conditions was done by **Sud, S.** It consists of 10 items on a 4 point scale and measures General Self Efficacy. This is a self-administered scale which normally takes two to three minutes to complete.

ANALYSIS OF DATA AND RESULTS

SELF EFFICACY OF SPECIAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

The overall Self Efficacy of special school teachers was measured. The Mean, S.D and other scores of Self Efficacy of special school teachers were computed as shown in the following table:

Table 1.:Descriptive Statistics of scores of Special School Teachers on Self Efficacy Scale

Self Efficacy	N	Range	Min	Max	Mean	S.D	KURT	SKEW
	200	30	10	40	30.15	4.71	1.60	-.528

From the above table, it is clear that the range of scores for over all self efficacy is **10-40** as the minimum and maximum scores for Self Efficacy is given 10 and 40 respectively. There is overall high Self Efficacy is found in special education teachers, because total mean value on job stressor scale was found (**30.15**). As the manual shows that the range of scores for over all Self Efficacy is 10-40 and as per the manual ,score 30 and above is considered as high self efficacy. Hence, it can be said that special school teachers have overall high self efficacy. From this result it can be said that special school teachers are confident enough to perform the work related to their occupation.

OCCUPATIONAL STRESS OF SPECIAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

Overall occupational stress of special school teachers was measured. The mean and S.D of scores of occupational stress and its sub dimensions of special school teachers were computed as shown in the following table:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of scores of Special School Teachers on TJSS

Dimensions of O.S.	N	Range	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Overloadedness (OL)	200	106	5	54	24.06	8.916
Role Conflict (RC)	200	22	12	34	21.87	5.586
Powerlessness (PL)	200	49	13	37	23.22	3.707
Role ambiguity(RA)	200	24	11	39	25.61	5.969
Motivelessness(ML)	200	28	10	35	21.23	6.286
Frail I.P.Relationship (FIR)	200	25	9	38	21.49	5.437
Overall Occupational Stress(OL)	200	29	87	193	137.50	24.603

From the above table, it is clear that the range of scores for over all stress is 87-193 as the minimum and maximum scores for occupational stress is given 87 and 193 respectively. There is overall mild occupational stress found in special education teachers, because total mean value on job stressor scale was found (**137.50**). As the manual shows that the range of scores for over all stress is 91-187. Mean value for special education teachers lies in the column of 128-154 i.e., above 50th percentile. Hence, it can be said that special school teachers feel overall mild stress in their occupation. The mean value for the sub dimension Overloadedness (**24.06**), Role conflict (**21.87**), powerlessness (**23.22**), Role Ambiguity (**25.61**), Motivelessness (**21.23**) and Frail interpersonal relationship is (**21.49**) Which lies on or above around 50th percentile. Therefore, it can be concluded that special school teachers feel mild Overloadedness, mild role conflict, feel mild powerlessness, mild role ambiguity, feel mild motivelessness and mild frail interpersonal relationship in their occupation.

IMPACT OF SELF EFFICACY ON OCCUPATIONAL STRESS OF SPECIAL SCHOOL TEACHERS

Following hypothesis was verified to examine the impact of self efficacy on occupational stress of Special School Teachers:

H₁: There exists no significant correlation between Occupational stress and self efficacy of Special School Teachers.

The Correlation Coefficient was computed to test this hypothesis. Statistical results are shown in the table given below.

Table 3. : Coefficient Correlation between Occupational Stress and Self Efficacy of Special School Teachers

Variables	N	df	r
Occupational Stress	200	198	0.122 (Non significant)
Self Efficacy			

The value in table 3 shows that the obtained value of correlation coefficient for occupational stress and self efficacy is **0.122**, which indicates that there is no correlation between Occupational stress and Self efficacy of Special School Teachers. As this value (0.122) falls between 0.00 and 0.20, which furthers enlighten that there is negligible correlation between these two variables. It means there is no effect of self efficacy on occupational stress. Therefore, the concerned null hypothesis H_1 is accepted. Furthermore it can be concluded that there is no effect of self efficacy on occupational stress of Special School Teachers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

There is overall high Self Efficacy is found in special education teachers. It can be concluded from it that special school teachers have a faith in themselves to perform their job related tasks. The reason behind this finding may be that all special school teachers are well trained before joining the school.

There is overall mild level of occupational stress found in teachers of special school. Moderate over-loadedness, role conflict, powerlessness, role ambiguity, motivelessness and frail interpersonal relationship were also found among this group of teachers. The causes for this finding may be that these teachers have to do lots of challenging task in their occupation. They have to deal with children and youth who have variety of disabilities. They have to develop individualized Education Programs (IEP) and to do lots of

paperwork. They also make such special need students learn routine activities and skills required for day to day life. Teachers also have to interact frequently with parents, social worker, psychologist and therapist. In this way their diverse nature of job might make them stressed. In the past the similar results were found by many researchers that Special School teachers are found experiencing moderate stress (**Maolin and Xiaoxin ,2008; Male and May ,1997**). This result is also in tune with the result of **Chakrawarti (1989) and Prasad (1990)**. They claim that teachers in special schools and classes may be *particularly* prone to stress related illness.

There is no correlation found between occupational stress and Self efficacy of Special School Teachers. In other words it can be said that there is no impact of self efficacy on occupational stress of Special School Teachers. It means they are no more related with each other. There is lack of evidences in support of this finding as the relation of occupational stress and self efficacy was no longer investigated by researchers. **Demirdag (2015)** investigated the correlation between teachers self efficacy and occupational satisfaction and found the same, non-significant and negative correlation between teacher self-efficacy and occupational satisfaction. Self efficacy is the self belief to do the particular task. It may be possible that as all teachers are well trained before joining the school and they all have high self efficacy to do their job. This may be the reason that there is no impact found of self efficacy on occupational stress of Special School Teachers.

SUGGESTIONS

It has been inferred in the light of this research that teachers of special school feel themselves stressed in their occupation. Stress directly affects the young children who are receiving education from such stressed teachers. Therefore there is a need to consider this seriously

and necessary steps and actions should be taken to reduce the stress level of teachers.

References

- Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Towards a unifying theory of behavioural change. *Psychological Review*, 84, 191-215.
- Bandura, A. (1995). Exercise of personal and collective efficacy in changing societies. in A.Bandura (Ed.), *Self-efficacy in changing societies* (pp. 1-45). New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Chakraverty,B. (1989) 'Mental health among school teachers', in M. Cole & S .Walker (eds.) *Teaching and Stress*. Milton Keynes: Open University Press.
- Demirdag,S.(2015). Assessing Teacher Self-Efficacy and Job Satisfaction: Middle School Teachers *Journal of Educational and Instructional Studies in the World*. 5 (3) ISSN: 2146-7463.
- Male, D. B. & May, D. (1997). Research Section: Stress, Burnout and Workload in Teachers of Children with Special Educational Needs. *British Journal of Special Education*, 24,133–140.
- Maolin,Z.,& Xiaoxin,D-U (2008). Dissertation, *A Study on the Job Stress and Coping Strategies of Special School Teachers*, College of Preschool and Special Education,
- East China Normal University,Shanghai,200062 and .Nanjing Technical College of Special Education,Nanjing,210038).
- Pepe,A.and Addimando,L.(2014). Comparison of Occupational Stress in Response to Challenging Behaviours between General and Special Education Primary Teachers in Northern Italy. *International Journal of Education*, 28(1), 14-26.
- Prasad, S.N.(1990).*Mental Health of Teachers*.New Delhi: Gian Publishing House.
- Rathode, M.B. & Verma, M. (2005). *Indore Teacher's Job Stressor Scale*, National Psychological Corporation, Agra.
- Sharma, U., Shaukat, S., & Furlonger, B. (2015). Attitudes and self-efficacy of pre-service teachers towards inclusion in Pakistan. *Journal of Research in Special Education Needs* 97-105.
- Sud, S. (2002). *General Self Efficacy Scale Hindi*, rupa Psychological Centre, Varanasi.